

M1 Real World Lab framing and actors involved

Tuesday, 30 September 2025

Valeria Pancioli⁸, Dominik Hedderich⁹, Jana Löhrllein¹¹, Paolo Mazzoli⁴, Max Steinhausen¹, Janne Parviainen¹⁸, Lydia Cumiskey⁶, Joanna Mau¹, Tobias Conradt², Martin Drews³, Emilie Rønde Nielsen⁷, Amalie Laursen⁷, Stefano Bagli⁴, Francesca Renzi⁴, Pia-Johanna Schweizer⁵, Sandro Nanni¹³, Christopher Genillard⁹, Stefan Hochrainer-Stigler¹⁰, Julian Struck¹¹, Levente Huszti¹², Heiko Apel¹⁴, Benedikt Gräler¹⁵, Chahan Kropf¹⁶, Tracy Irvine¹⁷, Sukaina Bharwani¹⁸

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG | 10. INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE |
| 2. POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV | 11. ERFTVERBAND |
| 3. DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET | 12. ZALA KULONLEGES MENTOK ES ONKENTES TUZOLTO EGYSULET |
| 4. GECOSISTEMA SRL | 13. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PREVENZIONE, L'AMBIENTE E L'ENERGIA DELL'EMILIA-ROMAGNA |
| 5. RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR SUSTAINABILITY | 14. HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM POTSDAM DEUTSCHESGEOFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GFZ |
| 6. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK – NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK | 15. 52 NORTH SPATIAL INFORMATION RESEARCH GMBH |
| 7. REGION HOVEDSTADEN | 16. EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH |
| 8. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA SICUREZZATERRITORIALE E LA PROTEZIONE CIVILE | 17. OASIS HUB LIMITED |
| 9. GENILLARD & CO GMBH | 18. SEI OXFORD OFFICE LIMITED |

Report overview

Project number	101073978
Project acronym	DIRECTED
Project name	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing Interoperable Data, Models, Communication and Governance
Call	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Action
Responsible service	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	01/10/2022
Project duration	4 Years
Period covered	1 October 2022 - 30 September 2026
Milestone due date	31 July 2023
Milestone submission date	9 August 2023

RWL meetings calendar and multi stakeholders lists

Hereafter we report the tables with lists of involved Stakeholders and meetings calendars for each RWL.

Index of Tables

Table 1: Stakeholders involved organizations in the RWL 1	5
Table 2: Meetings calendar for RWL 1	6
Table 3: Stakeholders involved organizations in the RWL 2.....	8
Table 4: Meetings calendar for RWL 2	9
Table 5: Stakeholder overview Vienna	10
Table 6: Stakeholder overview Zala County	11
Table 7: Stakeholder overview Belgrade.....	12
Table 8: Stakeholders involved and addressed in the RWL 4 Rhine-Erft Region.....	14
Table 9: Meetings RWL 4 Rhine-Erft Region.....	16

List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD	COMMENTS
Halsnæs Municipality	Municipality	CCA authority	Sea-level rise, storm surges, pluvial flooding, heat/drought.	Covers part of the coast towards Roskilde Fjord
Frederikssund Municipality	Municipality	CCA authority	Sea-level rise, storm surges, pluvial flooding, heat/drought.	Covers part of the coast towards Roskilde Fjord
Roskilde Municipality	Municipality	CCA authority	Sea-level rise, storm surges, pluvial flooding, heat/drought.	Covers part of the coast towards Roskilde Fjord
Lejre Municipality	Municipality	CCA authority	Sea-level rise, storm surges, pluvial flooding, heat/drought.	Covers part of the coast towards Roskilde Fjord
Egedal Municipality	Municipality	CCA authority	Pluvial flooding, fluvial flooding, heat/drought, storm surges.	Downstream of Værebro Å, no coast but can be affected by storm surges from Roskilde Fjord
Frederiksborg Brand og Redning	Emergency Management/Fire Department	First responders in DRM locally	Floods and fire	Covers five municipalities including Halsnæs, Frederikssund and Egedal.
Roskilde Brand	Emergency Management/Fire Department	First responders in DRM locally	Floods and fire	Covers only Roskilde Municipality
Lejre Brandvæsen	Emergency Management/Fire Department	First responders in DRM locally	Floods and fire	Covers only Lejre Municipality
The Danish Emergency Management Agency	National emergency management agency	Responsible for DRR and DRM nationally	“Disasters”	
Danish Meteorological Institute	National weather and climate agency	Meteorological knowledge, data and warnings on weather, climate, and sea. Both used in CCA/ DRM.	All	Is currently developing a new warning system for floods
The Danish Coastal Authority	National government agency for the	Regulation of the coastal zone in CCA	Coast-related hazards	

	coastal zone			
Region Zealand	Regional government	No official role in CCA or DRM except for involvement of the health sector in DRM	All	Part of Roskilde Fjord and the municipalities are in Region Zealand. See flowchart below

Table 1: Stakeholders involved organizations in the RWL 1.

MEETING	LOCATION/ ONLINE	DATE (DD/MM/YY)	PARTICIPANTS	COMMENTS
Bilateral introduction meetings with stakeholders	Online	05/01/23 - 20/01/23	The Danish Emergency Management Agency, Egedal Municipality, Frederikssund Municipality, Roskilde Brand, Halsnæs Municipality, Frederiksborg Brand og Redning, REGIONH	
RWL workshop	Hillerød, Denmark (in person)	03/03/23	Egedal Municipality, Frederiksborg Brand og Redning, The Danish Emergency Management Agency, Frederikssund Municipality, Halsnæs Municipality, Region Zealand, Lejre Brandvæsen, REGIONH, DTU	17 participants in total
Mini workshop	Roskilde (in person)	02/05/23	Roskilde Brand, Roskilde Municipality, REGIONH, DTU	

Table 2: Meetings calendar for RWL 1.

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD	COMMENTS
Regional Protected Areas, Forests, and mountain areas development sector	Regional Government	CCA	Forest Fire	
Regional Soil Defence Sector - Geology, Soils and Seismic Area	Regional Government	DRR	Coastal Risk, hydrogeological Risk	Covers the entire regional territory, uses data and models to support knowledge of hydrogeological risk and coastal risk
Po Delta Parks and biodiversity management body	National Government	CCA	Forest Fire	
Ferrara provincial civil protection voluntary coordination	Provincial Government	DRM	ALL	Supports emergency management in the province of Ferrara
Rimini provincial civil protection voluntary coordination	Provincial Government	DRM	ALL	Supports emergency management in the province of Rimini
Comacchio Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Mesola Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Riccione Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Rimini Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD	COMMENTS
Bellaria Igea Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Misano Adriatic Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Cattolica Municipality	Municipal Government	DRR/CCA	ALL	Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
HERA SPA	Essential services Provider			Municipal competent authority, is the first entity that responds to emergencies in competence and is responsible for the implementation of the municipal civil protection plan, uses data and models
Biodiversity Police	National Government	DRR/CCA	Forest Fire	
Romagna Reclamation consortium		DRR/CCA	Hydraulic Risk	Manages the minor artificial hydraulic network of the plain in the Romagna area, supports emergency management, uses data and models
Riviera del Conca Civil Protection operative centre	Municipal Government	DRM	ALL	Inter-municipal civil protection operations centre for the municipalities of Cattolica, Coriano, Misano Adriatico, Riccione, San Giovanni in Marignano

Table 3: Stakeholders involved organizations in the RWL 2.

MEETING	LOCATION/ ONLINE	DATE (DD/MM/YY)	PARTICIPANTS	COMMENTS
RWL 2 Meeting	Bologna	21/03/2023	Civil Protection Agency Emilia-Romagna Region, Environmental Agency Emilia-Romagna Region, Comacchio Municipality, Mesola Municipality, Ferrara provincial civil protection voluntary coordination, Po Delta Parks and biodiversity management body, Regional Protected Areas, Forests and mountain areas development sector, Riccione Municipality, Rimini Municipality, Bellaria Igea Municipality, Misano adriatico Municipality, Rimini provincial civil protection voluntary coordination, HERA SPA - Provider of essential services, Regional Soil Defence Sector - Geology, Soils and Seismic Area	
RWL 2, 2° Meeting	September 2023	September 2023	Civil Protection Agency Emilia-Romagna Region, Environmental Agency Emilia-Romagna Region, Comacchio Municipality, Mesola Municipality, Ferrara provincial civil protection voluntary coordination, Po Delta Parks and biodiversity management body, Regional Protected Areas, Forests and mountain areas development sector, Riccione Municipality, Rimini Municipality, Bellaria Igea Municipality, Misano adriatico Municipality, Rimini provincial civil protection voluntary coordination, HERA SPA - Provider of essential services, Regional Soil Defence Sector - Geology, Soils and Seismic Area	Initially scheduled for May, postponed due to the tragic events that hit the Region in May.

Table 4: Meetings calendar for RWL 2.

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD
Viadonau.org	Regional	DRM	Flood
Red Cross Austria	National	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake
Disaster Risk Management - Salzburg	Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake
VVÖ – Insurance Association Austria	National	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
Uniqa – Insurance	National	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
VIG - Insurance	International	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
Generali-Insurance	International	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences-BOKU	National	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought
European Commission/ JRC	International	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
Central Institute for Meteorology and Geothermal Energy (ZAMG)	National	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Earthquake, Hail
Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions, and Water Management	National	CCA	Drought, Flood, Hail, Storm

Table 5: Stakeholder overview Vienna.

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD
West Transdanubia Water Directorate	water treatment and management	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought
Association of Volunteer Firefighters	Fire prevention, fire rescue, etc. – Regional	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
Zala County Territorial Protection Committee	Territorial protection and administration – Regional	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm
MouldTech Systems	Tech-company – Regional	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought
City of Nagykanizsa	Local municipality – Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
Municipality of Zala County	County municipality – Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
Hungarian Road Department	Road Operator – Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
City of Zalaegerszeg	Local municipality - Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
Zalaerdö PLc.	Forest Management, Woodwork – Regional	DRM/CCA	Drought
National Association for Radio Emergency and Info communications	professional activity - related to the enhancement of road traffic and water safety – National	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
EDER STT Special Tank Transport	hazardous material transfer, ADR – National	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm
Zala County Disaster Management Directorate	Disaster management – National	DRM/CCA	Flood, Drought, Storm, Hail
Town of Keszthely	Local Municipality – Regional	DRM	Flood, Drought, Storm

Table 6: Stakeholder overview Zala County.

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD
Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia	Hydrometeorological early warning system - National	CCA	Drought, Flood, Storm, Hail
Vode Vojdovine	Public Water Management Company, Novi Sad - Regional	DRM/CCA	Drought, Flood
Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health, Faculty of Technical Sciences,	University of Novi Sad - Regional/National	DRM/CCA	Drought, Flood, Storm, Hail
UOS Insurance Association	Belgrade - Regional	DRM/CCA	Drought, Flood, Storm, Hail

Table 7: Stakeholder overview Belgrade.

ORGANIZATION	GROUP	PHASE OF DRM/CCA	HAZARD	COMMENTS
Environment and Planning Department	District of Euskirchen	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	-
Civil Protection	District of Euskirchen	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	-
Department of Rescue, Fire and Civil Protection	District of Rhine-Erft	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	-
Department for Technical Environment Protection	District of Rhine-Erft	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	-
District of Rhein-Sieg	District	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
District of Rhein-Neuss	District	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
District of Düren	District	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA regionally	All	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
Municipalities of the district of Euskirchen (Bad Münstereifel, Blankenheim, Dahlem, Euskirchen, Hellenthal, Kall, Mechernich, Nettersheim, Schleiden, Weilerswist and Zulpich)	Municipalities	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA locally	All	have shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
Municipalities of the district of Rhein-Erft (Bedburg, Bergheim, Brühl, Elsdorf, Erftstadt, Frechen, Hürth, Kerpen, Pulheim and Wesseling)	Municipalities	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA locally	All	have shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
Municipalities of the district of Rhein-Sieg (Alfter, Bad Honnef, Bornheim, Eitorf, Hennef, Königswinter, Lohmar, Meckenheim, Much, Neunkirchen Seelscheid,	Municipalities	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA locally	All	have shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet

Niederkassel, Rheinbach, Ruppichteroth, Sankt Augustin, Siegburg, Swisttal, Troisdorf, Wachtberg, Windeck)				
Municipalities of the district of Düren (Aldenhoven, Düren, Heimbach, Hürtgenwald, Inden, Jülich Kreuzau, Langerwehe, Linnich, Merzenich, Nideggen, Niederzier, Nörvenich, Titz, Vettweiß) interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet	Municipalities	Responsible for DRR, DRM and CCA locally	All	have shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
State Agency for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection (LANUV)	State Agency	DRR, DRM and CCA	All	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
VdS Schadenverhütung GmbH	Insurance company	Prevention, Preparedness	Flooding	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet
Hydraulic Engineering and Water Management	University of Kaiserslautern - Landau (RPTU)	Prevention, Preparedness	Flooding	has shown interest in participating in DIRECTED, but no signed letter of engagement yet

Table 8: Stakeholders involved and addressed in the RWL 4 Rhine-Erft Region.

MEETING	LOCATION/ ONLINE	DATE (DD/MM/YY)	PARTICIPANTS	COMMENTS
First meeting with stakeholders	online	19/04/23	Jana Löhrlin (DIRECTED-project, Ertfverband - EV), Dr. Julian Struck (project manager of the intermunicipal flood protection corporation, Ertfverband), Dr. Daniel Bittner (head of department of river basin management, Ertfverband), Marcel Schneider (team leader - water & soil conservation; district of Euskirchen), Martin Fehrmann (head of department of civil protection; district of Euskirchen), Peter Jonas (employee department of civil protection; district of Euskirchen), Sarah Nolting (reconstruction unit, leader of the project KRITIS-Dialog; district of Euskirchen), Christine Bernt (head of department of technical environmental protection; district of Rhine-Erft), Thomas Weiler (head of department of rescue, fire and civil protection; district of Rhine-Erft)	-
Second stakeholder meeting	Bergheim (in person)	29/06/23	Jana Löhrlin (DIRECTED-project, Ertfverband), Dr. Julian Struck (project manager of the intermunicipal flood protection corporation, Ertfverband), Dr. Dietmar Jansen (head of division surface waters, Ertfverband), Per Seeliger (lawyer, Ertfverband), Dr. Daniel Bittner (head of department of river basin management, Ertfverband), Ulrich Muris (head of department river maintenance water operations, Ertfverband), Dr. Tilo Keller (team leader hydrology measurements and data management, Ertfverband), Timo Schneider (project manager in the department of surface waters, Ertfverband), Marcel Schneider (team leader - water & soil conservation; district of Euskirchen), Hartwig Kaven (employee water & soil conservation, district of Euskirchen), Peter Jonas (employee department of civil protection; district of Euskirchen), Sarah Nolting (reconstruction unit, leader of the project KRITIS-Dialog; district of Euskirchen),	-

MEETING	LOCATION/ ONLINE	DATE (DD/MM/YY)	PARTICIPANTS	COMMENTS
			Christine Bernt (head of department of technical environmental protection; district of Rhine-Erft), Thomas Weiler (head of department of rescue, fire and civil protection; district of Rhine-Erft)	
First contact and introduction DIRECTED - VdS Schadenverhütung GmbH	Bergheim (in person)	30/06/23	Jana Löhrllein (DIRECTED project, Erftverband), Dr. Julian Struck (project manager of the intermunicipal flood protection corporation, Erftverband), Bettina Falkenhagen (VdS Schadenverhütung GmbH)	Showed interest in participating in DIRECTED (no signed letter of engagement yet)
First contact and introduction DIRECTED - department of hydraulic engineering and water management RPTU Kaiserlautern - Landau	Online	04/07/23	Jana Löhrllein (DIRECTED-project, Erftverband), Dr. Julian Struck (project manager of the intermunicipal flood protection corporation, Erftverband), Prof. Dr. Robert Jüpner (head of department of hydraulic engineering and water management RPTU Kaiserlautern - Landau), Dr.-Ing. Martin Fabisch (head of the department of surveying and geoinformation), Dr.-Ing. Hellen Hammoudi (research associate in the department of hydraulic engineering and water management), Selina Schaum (research associate in the department of hydraulic engineering and water management), Luzie Kretschmer (research associate in the department of hydraulic engineering and water management)	Showed interest in participating in DIRECTED (no signed letter of engagement yet)

Table 9: Meetings RWL 4 Rhine-Erft Region.

Partners

